

Current Stages and Goals of Russian Language Science

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Abstract: This article discusses the objectives of the subject Russian language, the features of the process of formation of foreign language speech activity and the components that determine its content - language material, theoretical information about the language and the skills to operate with them. Communication, speech skills; themes and situations, each of the named components performs its own functions.

Keywords: Task, components, skill, skills, function, mastery, development, scientific, general scientific, bilingualism, bilingualism, subject, formation, option, invariant, regional, national, typical.

Introduction

The objectives of the subject Russian language, the features of the process of formation of foreign language speech activity determine its content, which includes the following components: language material, theoretical information about the language and the skills to operate with them; communication, speech skills; themes and situation; general educational skills. Each of these components performs its own functions and at the same time is connected with others.

Language material, theoretical information about language. A prerequisite for mastering the Russian language as a means of communication is the assimilation of the nuclear microsystem of the language, the necessary and sufficient minimum of language material and information about the language, on the basis of which students' speech activity is formed. At the same time, it seems legitimate that linguodidactics proposes to isolate, on the one hand, the language material itself (a minimum of words, phraseological units) and information about the language (rules, definitions, terms), on the basis of which students' speech activity is formed, and, on the other hand, the skills of operating it. In other words, this component includes both educational material and those skills that are formed on its basis (lexical, grammatical, etc.).

Currently, the role of systemic information about the Russian language is increasing. This is determined by the task of the interconnected study of Russian and the native language of students: information about linguistic phenomena and facts presented in a certain system contributes to the formation of knowledge and representation in the Russian language, about categories and concepts that are not in the native language, and thereby makes possible a deeper knowledge of the native language, have a positive impact on the culture of native speech.

Speech skills. The second component of the content of the Russian language subject - speech skills - reflects the practical purpose of training. The selection of this component is an achievement of modern methods of teaching Russian as a national language and reflects its speech orientation. Its main purpose is to determine the scope and boundaries of communication skills that should be developed in students. These are the skills and abilities to understand Russian speech by ear, speak, write, read in Russian. Each type of speech activity is characterized by its own inherent skills and abilities.

Methodology

Topics and situations. The ultimate goal of teaching the Russian language in national groups is fluency in speech. However, while studying at school, it is unlikely that verbal communication skills can be developed in all the variety of topics and situations in real life. Therefore, the subject Russian language includes a thematic and content component. It consists of topics and situations within which graduates of national universities should be able to communicate freely in Russian.

This component determines the extra-linguistic boundaries of the implementation of the practical goal of learning, reality, on the material and within which the speech activity of students is formed. The thematic-content component determines the cognitive-educational educational material of the subject, on the basis of which its most important function is realized - educating the personality of the future specialist. Topics reflect that part of the social experience of the Uzbek people that students will learn in Russian language lessons; they provide a targeted selection of meaningful educational material and thus make the process of educating students through the means of the subject itself to a certain extent manageable.

For the scientific development of the problem of a minimum of topics for speech development, it is necessary to define the concept of "topics for speech development" as a category of linguodidactics, principles and sources for identifying these topics, outline their nomenclature, main aspects and directions of disclosure, distribute topics and subtopics according to the stages of training.

In modern methods of teaching the Russian language, there is a desire to bring the learning process as close as possible to real communication. In this regard, speech situations are recognized in the practice of national universities. Their use increases the effectiveness of teaching verbal communication and contributes to the formation and development of interest in the Russian language. They are sufficiently reflected in existing programs; they are used in the educational process.

The scientific justification of the thematic and content component includes, in addition to determining a minimum of topics, the development of a situational minimum, or a minimum of speech situations. Based on existing research and the structure of speech situations, the following directions for its development are identified. First of all, the situational minimum should include not isolated communication situations, but typical or stable situations; they should not represent specific speech situations, but an inventory that includes lists of:

communicative needs of students in real areas of communication (request for information, encouragement to take action, etc.);

social and communicative roles, typical and natural for verbal communication of students;

places of speech communication (university, street, post office, etc.).

It is important to determine the content of the Russian language subject in national universities to identify the correlation between situations and language material. This problem has been largely solved at the level of speech actions. Further study taking into account its other components is necessary.

General educational skills and abilities. The fourth component, general educational skills, occupies a special place in the content of the Russian language subject. The reforms of the university program provide for comprehensive preparation of students for future practical activities. This means that they must have developed the skills and mental work necessary to obtain further education and active participation in society.

Already in the lessons of the native language and native literature, general educational skills and independent work skills that are important for practical activities in the future are formed, such as drawing up a plan, theses, determining the main thing in the content of a text, the ability to use dictionaries, etc. In the process of mastering the Russian language, these skills must be improved using other language material. For example, skills in working with a monolingual dictionary, acquisition in

native language lessons, can be developed using the material of various types of Russian language dictionaries, etc.

In the conditions of the formation of national-Russian bilingualism, the named components of the content of the Russian language subject in national groups must be coordinated with the corresponding components of the native language subject.

Results and discussion

Thus, it is necessary to distribute theoretical (linguistic) material between the native and Russian languages, to correlate the metalanguage, terminological apparatus, the volume and nature of the skills of monologue dialogic speech, topics and situations for the development of speech, etc. Coordination between the Russian language and the native language will ensure a unified linguistic and the speech basis for the formation and development of national-Russian bilingualism.

Invariant and option. The development of the problem of the content of teaching the Russian language in our multinational country is always associated with solving problems of typical and variable ones. To what extent are standard solutions possible? Where mandatory, it is necessary to take into account the peculiarities of the functioning of the Russian language in specific conditions. This problem is of particular relevance nowadays due to the fact that the development of individual abilities of students and differentiated training in accordance with their needs and inclinations are named as a key direction in the reform of higher education.

The unity of goals and objectives of education should be organically combined with the diversity of universities and the flexibility of curricula and programs.

The subject Russian language in national groups contains such basic educational material that is necessary and sufficient for mastering the Russian language as a means of interethnic communication. This material should form a typical part of the content of the subject, the assimilation of which is necessary, regardless of the type of higher education institution and the conditions of functioning of the Russian language.

The legitimacy and expediency of a typical, content-invariant Russian language subject in national groups is determined by:

the status of the Russian language as a means of interethnic communication between the peoples of our country, determined by the internationalization of the entire life of society;

the presence of common directions in the development of national-Russian bilingualism;

the unity of goals and objectives of education solved by the national university;

the unity of the subject of study and the universal nature of a significant part of the difficulties of Russian as a non-native language, common to all national universities;

general patterns of teaching Russian as a non-native language and its assimilation in national populations.

The identification of a content invariant that reflects the specifics of the Russian language, its topological features, justifies the basic component of the content of the Russian language subject for national groups of universities in our country.

The variation in the content of the Russian language subject is determined primarily by the type of university, the problems that it is designed to solve (obvious, for example, differences in the humanities, physico-mathematical, chemical-biological and other specialties).

The diversity of regional and national conditions for the functioning of the Russian language, the formation of national-Russian bilingualism in the presence and degree of spread of the Russian speech environment, natural speech contacts, the relationship between Russian and native languages, the traditions of teaching the Russian language, also determines the variation in the content of the Russian

language subject in national universities. In this case, the need and purposefulness of the varied part of the content of the subject are determined by:

the impact of students' native language on the acquisition of Russian (the nature and types of interference and transposition of students' native language).

The presence of the basic Russian language, which constitutes the communicative-pragmatic and structure-forming core, necessary and at the same time sufficient for mastering the Russian language as a means of communication, justifies the standard language content, one and the same for all students. It was reflected in the aspect minima, the "Model Program for the Russian Language".

The variation of linguistic material, theoretical information about language (the first component of the content of the Russian language subject mentioned above) is determined primarily by the variety of types of schools. For example, schools with a humanitarian profile may provide for a higher level of mastery of it. Variation in the language component may also be due to the consideration of the native language and the orientation of the subject to a specific national school. What are the directions and boundaries of variation in linguistic content? This question must be answered by methodological science, by methodologists who develop programs and textbooks for national schools in the union and autonomous republics.

The thematic and content component of training also includes standard and variable parts. The set of topics and situations is open-ended. A certain part of it is of a standard nature and is recommended for all universities of the republic, because we are talking about the content aspect of teaching the Russian language, which forms common, unified ideological, social, cultural, and intellectual qualities of the personality of a modern person. However, highlighting the invariant basis of the thematic and content component of teaching the Russian language in no way means its strict regulation.

The problem of the typical part of the thematic and content component has already been solved to a certain extent. In the standard Russian language program for national groups, approximate topics for speech development are identified and their specification in subtopics is proposed. Thus, we can already talk about developing a unified thematic and content basis for the course. However, such an important component of the content structure as the situation has not received sufficient justification.

Conclusion

The thematic-content component of training, in addition to standard material, includes variable: topics, subtopics, situations that reflect the characteristics of culture, life of the republic, and the specifics of the functioning of the Russian language in a particular university. The variability of the content of the subject of the Russian language in the thematic and substantive terms can manifest itself in the nature of the disclosure of topics, situations, in the volume and nature of information from literary, situational, thematic and regional studies material.

Strict regulation of the sequence of topics is probably not advisable. Of course, a certain part of them, associated, for example, with the seasons and holidays, can be correlated with the corresponding periods of study. However, the sequence of introduction of the main part of the topics is conditional.

The problem of standard and variable takes on particular relevance in determining the structure of a subject, its construction, and, consequently, in developing programs for specific universities. In the context of the diversity of universities, in the different conditions of the formation of national-Russian bilingualism, other solutions are possible and, probably, should be. In this case, the structure of the subject of the native language can play an important role - after all, the formation of national-Russian bilingualism makes the problem of correlating the content of the subjects Russian and the native language relevant.

In conclusion, it should be said that various solutions to the problem of the content of the Russian language subject in a national audience are undoubtedly possible, however, the proposed concepts for constructing this subject should ensure the implementation of the goals of teaching the Russian

language - the language of introducing every graduate of national groups to culture, social and labor activities on a state scale

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